

MIRSIDDIQ HASHMAT BUKHARY-PRIVATE LIBRARY OF SAYID MUHAMMAD MIR SIDDIQHON (HASHMAT)

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Annotation: *This article is devoted to the description of the personal library of Mir Muhammad Siddiq Khashmat, a writer, poet and scientist who lived in Bukhara in the late 19th - early 20th century and made a great contribution to the cultural and educational life of Central Asia. a valuable source of many works and their authors. tells about strange events connected with the calligraphers who copied them.*

Keywords: *Mir Muhammad Mirsiddiq Hashmat, Mustaqillik, Bukhara, Khiva, Ko'kan, Uzbekistan, Tazkira, Amir Temur, Sadr Zia, Sadriddin Ainiy, "Tazkirat-ush-shuaro", calligrapher, personal library.*

МИРСИДДИК ХАШМАТ БУХАРЫ-ЧАСТНАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА САИДА МУХАММАДА МИР СИДДИКХОНА (ХАШМАТ)

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Аннотация: *Данная статья посвящена описанию личной библиотеки Мир Мухаммада Сиддика Хашимата, писателя, поэта и ученого, жившего в Бухаре в конце XIX - начале XX века и внесшего большой вклад в культурно-просветительскую жизнь Средней Азии. ценный источник многих произведений и их авторов. повествует о странных событиях, связанных с переписавшими их каллиграфами.*

Ключевые слова: *Мир Мухаммад Мирсиддик Хашиमत, Мустакиллик, Бухара, Хива, Кокан, Узбекистан, Тазкира, Амир Темур, Садр Зия, Садриддин Айний, «Тазкират-уш-шуаро», каллиграф, личная библиотека.*

MIRSIDDIQ HASHMAT BUXORIY-SAYYID MUHAMMAD MIR SIDDIQHON (HASHMAT) NING SHAXSIY KUTUBXONASI

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Annotation: *XIX asr oxiri-XX asr boshida Buxoroda yashab, O‘rta Osiyo madaniy-ma‘rifiy hayotiga ulkan hissa qo‘shgan adib, shoir va olim hamda xushnavis xattot Mir Muhammad Siddiq Hashmatning o‘z shaxsiy kutubxonasi tavsifiga oid mazkur maqola qimmatli manba bo‘lishi bilan barobar juda ko‘p asarlar va ularning mualliflari, ularni ko‘chirgan xattotlar bilan bog‘liq g‘aroyib hodisalar haqida hikoya qiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Mir Muhammad Mirsiddiq Hashmat, Mustaqillik, Buxoro, Xiva, Qo‘qon, O‘zbekiston, Tazkira, Amir Temur, Sadr Ziyo, Sadridin Ayniy, “Tazkirat-ush-shuaro”, xattot, shaxsiy kutubxona.*

Mirsiddiq Hashmat Bukhari, a writer, poet and scientist, who lived in Bukhara in the late 19th - early 20th century and made a great contribution to the cultural and educational life of Central Asia, is considered an intellectual compatriot who left behind scientific and artistic works on various topics. . According to the tradition of that time, Mirsiddiq Hashmat created his works in the Persian-Tajik language. But unfortunately, his life path and rich literary and historical heritage have been little studied, and only two or three works have been published in the Persian-Tajik language.

In this article, Mirsiddiq Hashmat’s zealous work in order to pass on the rare manuscript books, which are considered priceless wealth, to the next generation, and the description of these ancient heritage examples created by Uzbek, Arab, and Persian thinkers, as well as valuable information about the life and work of the calligraphers who copied these unique works data is referenced.

The cities of Uzbekistan have long been famous for as centers of science, and libraries have played a major role in this. Especially in the 9th-12th centuries, during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids, huge libraries were established in the country, and science flourished. In the following centuries, in particular, during the Khanate period, large libraries operated in the palaces of the rulers in the large cities of the region, in particular, in the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, and Ko‘kan.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, in the Emirate of Bukhara, along with scientific and literary circles, there were (mostly) communities, madrasas and mosques in regional centers, libraries near factories. In the libraries of this period there are books in Hindi, Uyghur, Pashto, Persian, Tajik, Arabic, Turkish and other languages.

In the Bukhara Emirate, state and public libraries, as well as private libraries, have shown wide activity. Private libraries were rich in rare books. Private libraries of Sharifjon-Makhdum Sadri Zia, Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat and Qazi Burhoniddin can be cited as an example.

Similarly, Qazi Abdulvahid Sadri Sariri Balkhi, Mir Siddiq Khan Hashmat, Nasir Khan Tora, Mufti Khatlani Sadridin and his son Burkhaniddin also had a prestigious library. Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat Library is one of the most prestigious libraries in Bukhara region after Sadri Zia Library.

According to Sadri Zia, at the beginning of the 20th century, there were 13 libraries and 96 reading rooms in the city of Bukhara alone. Manuscripts in Chinese, Uyghur, Pashto, Persian, Arabic and other languages are stored in the library of the ruler's palace in Bukhara. Librarians, bookkeepers, pamphleteers and mirzas served in the library. Along with the personal collections of the emirs, 47,500 volumes of manuscripts and lithographic books in various languages are stored in the palace library. The richest private library in the city of Bukhara belonged to Amirzada Hashmat. He was the son of the emir of Bukhara, Muzaffar, and he left several works. There were also several large private libraries in the country.

Regarding the family status and lineage of Mir-Siddiq Khan Hashmat, it can be said that he was born from the same mother as Prince Abdul Malik Tora and Nasir Khan Tora. When Amir Muzaffar (that is, the father of Hashmat I.E.) was alive, at the age of 17, Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat was appointed governor of Chorchui. After the death of Amir Muzaffar in 1885, when his brother Amir Abdulahad Khan came to the throne, Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat was sentenced to house arrest. Soon, Amirzada Nasirkhan will also be placed under house arrest. Abdul Malik, the third brother of Abdulahad Khan, was a lifelong traveler. According to Uzbek researcher Zahidova, Prince Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat and Nasir Khan Tora were also deprived of their freedom during the reign of Olim Khan, the son of S.Abdulahad Khan (68, 48-52). Meanwhile, only Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat is in prison for 35 years. Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat and Nasir Khan-Tora were deprived of all administrative, political and social work. However, Amir Abdulahad Khan and his son Olim Khan Mirsiddiq Khan did not create any obstacles or problems for the scientific and creative activities of Hashmat and Nasir Khan. It is for this reason that Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat and Nasir Khantora continued to study until the end of their lives, created a series of works, and made an incomparable contribution to the cultural, literary and spiritual life of Bukhara. In the research sources and traces of the owner of the library of both, the brothers: Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat and Nasir Khan-tora are highlighted.

Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat lived in Charharros yard of Bukhara city. Although his freedom was limited, his yard held an important place as a place of learning and knowledge for writers and people of words. Perhaps this is due to the influence of the literary environment, which later left a number of monuments and a large library. Connoisseurs and scholars of his time recognized Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat as a property owner, patron, patron of writers, poet, historian, owner of a prestigious library. As mentioned above, at the beginning of the 20th century, the yard of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat became the residence of poets, orators, people related to science and literature who were against the government of the emirs Abdul Ahad Khan and Olim Khan, where evenings were held with the participation of intellectuals. One of the important things that Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat did during his years in prison was to collect the works of his predecessors and create a large library. Mirsiddikhan Hashmat library is part of the history of Bukhara library.

According to Sharifjon-Makhdum Sadri Zia, one of the skilled calligraphers, Yakkaboghi's secretary, Abdullabek, copied the three-volume book of the Qur'an. One copy of it was kept in the treasury of Bukhara state, and the second copy was kept in the hands of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat. Mentioning the rare importance of Hashmat Mirsiddiq Khan's library, Ustoz Sadridin Aini says: "There was no library as perfect as Hashmat's private library in Bukhara."

Professor Shodmon Vahidov listed the contents of the library of Mirsiddikhan Hashmat, which consists of 1000 manuscripts and lithographs in different languages. In particular, he evaluates the role and significant contribution of the library of Mirsiddikhan Hashmat in the development and growth of the literary life of the Bukhara emirate as follows: played a role."

The historical and cultural significance of the library of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat is that the reader becomes aware of the existence of a series of inaccessible sources. In our opinion, the determination of the fate of his manuscripts sheds light on a number of historical issues and uncertain aspects related to the socio-political situation of Bukhara, which is one of the important issues of researching Uzbek literature and history. Shodmon Vahidov Mirsiddiq Khan emphasizes the important aspect for us that the books collected by Hashmat were preserved only due to the efforts of Sharifjan-Makhdum Sadr Zia: "We think that Hashmat collected these oriental manuscripts before moving to Afghanistan Sadr may have sold out to Zia. That's why we presented multi-part works in the Sadr Zia library.

Studying the structure and formation process of Mirsiddikhan Hashmat library is important from the point of view of librarianship and resource studies. The catalog of the library in Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat's house, Hashmat seals on books, reserve

marks, memories and notes of his contemporaries can be clarified and restored through the works of Sharifjon-Makhdum Sadr Zia. Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat himself recorded the name, author and secretary of 213 volumes of books and collections in his library, and sometimes also the price of the books he bought. In particular, his library contains "Ehyo Ulum ad-Din" by Muhammad Ghazali, "Akhloqi Nasiri" by Nasirud-Dini Tusi, works of Bedil, Sa'di and Hafiz, various bayozs, tazkiras, religious works, commentaries, columns on ada. - there was biology, astrology, history, etc.

The library of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat contains only such manuscripts and lithographs related to history: "History of Ibn Khaldun", "History of Afghanistan", "History of Andalus", "History of Javdat", "History of Rahimkhan", "History of Russia". "History of Iran Travel", "History of Shahjahan", "History of Tabari (Tarikh ar-rusul wal-muluk)", "History of the Greek War", "History of Abd ar-Rahman Khan", "History of Abdulhamid Khan", "General History", "History of Farishta", "History of Farangi", "History of Kojor", "History of Kashkar", "History of Medina", "History of Indo-Turktozon", "History of Wassaf" and others.

From comments and observations, it is known that most of the works of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat and his library have existed until our time, and some of them are kept as rare copies in the databases of major libraries of the world. In addition, most of the manuscripts and rare copies of the treasury of manuscripts of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Aburaykhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan were created at the expense of the Sharifjan-Makhdum Sadri Zia library and are related to the literary situation and social life of Bukhara in the early 19th-20th centuries. Mirsiddi Khan Hashmat - provides information up to the 20th century.

In addition, the analysis of the influence and position of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat library from the point of view of literary studies and historiography was carried out in the dissertations of professor Shodmon Vahidov.

Consequently, the researchers spoke about Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat's livelihood and condition, relying on and using the information of Ustad Sadridin Aini's "Sample of Tajik Literature". At the moment, the contribution of Rasul Hadizoda and Usman Karimov is significant among modern researchers in recognizing the lifestyle and creativity of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat. The Tajik scholar Rasul Hadizoda provides information about the life and work of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat, as well as the existence of sketches, notebooks and notes in his two works "Istochniki izucheniya tajikskoy literary vtoroy poloviny XIX veka" and "Adabiyoti Tajik dar nimai duvumi asri XIX". Usman Karimov expressed some new ideas about the work of Mirsiddiq Khan Hashmat using the materials of Rasul Hadizoda books. In addition,

the works of historians and literary scholars Zarif Rajabov, Tursunboy Nematzoda, Uzbek researchers Aziz Qayumov, Ghulam Karimov contain various details of his life and the names of his works.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the leaders of the Jadidist movement founded the first public libraries in order to widely promote enlightenment in the cities of the region. The literature collected in these libraries, which were established at the expense of their personal funds and donations, differed from the palace libraries in terms of content and direction, reflected the spirit of the times, and had an important role in shaping the worldview of the masses, especially young people.

In those days, the main purpose of creating libraries was first of all to regularly familiarize young people, school teachers, madrasa students, intellectuals with new literature, textbooks, press. Because it was impossible to find these literatures and newspapers anywhere else.

Today, the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, is of incomparable importance for instilling noble values and traditions in the life of the society, especially in raising the spiritual and intellectual potential of our people, especially the young generation, in raising the consciousness and worldview, in raising a well-rounded person who lives with love and loyalty to the Motherland and its people. paying particular attention to increasing the culture of reading, on January 13, 2017 and on September 13 of this year, "Comprehensive measures for the development of the system of publishing and distribution of book products, increasing and promoting book reading and reading culture "On the program" and on the establishment of a commission on the promotion of reading, local governments in each city and district to establish specialized book sales shops, to support them, benefit business entities with the status of a legal entity. It is planned to ensure the free use of unused state-owned objects, to form their material and technical base, and most importantly, to establish modern-type bookstores.

The work in this regard will definitely bear fruit one day. Already, our President, "You cannot achieve development and high spirituality without books" - Every country in the world, every nation is powerful primarily with its intellectual potential and high spirituality. The source of such invincible power is, first of all, the great discovery of human thinking - books and libraries.

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